

THE ART OF LETTER WRITING

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ABSTRACT

The current article is devoted to exploration of letter writing, its types, its definition and the very idea in the field of science and law. The article talks about goals, objectives and tasks of letter writing. Letters are short reports of original research focused on an outstanding finding whose importance means that it will be of interest to scientists in other fields.

Letter is an acceptable format for making comments on an article published in previously published issues of the same journal. Sometimes the letter may be related to an article published in a different journal. Letters are always written to the editor, they are never addressed to the first authors.

A letter is a written message that can be handwritten or printed on paper. It is usually sent to the recipient via mail or post in an envelope, although this is not a requirement as such. Any such message that is transferred via post is a letter, a written conversation between two parties.

However, even today a lot of our communication, especially the **formal kind**, is done via letters. Whether it is a cover letter for a job, or the bank sending you a reminder or a college acceptance letter, letters are still an important mode of communication.

Types of Letters

Let us first understand that there are broadly two types of letter, namely Formal Letters, and Informal Letters. But then there are also a few types of letters based on their contents, formalities, the purpose of letter writing etc. Let us have a look at the few types of letters.

- **Formal Letter:** These letters follow a certain pattern and formality. They are strictly kept professional in nature, and directly address the issues concerned. Any type of business letter or letter to authorities falls within this given category.
- **Informal Letter:** These are personal letters. They need not follow any set pattern or adhere to any formalities. They contain personal information or are a written conversation. Informal letters are generally written to friends, acquaintances, relatives etc.
- **Business Letter:** This letter is written among business correspondents, generally contains commercial information such as quotations, orders, complaints, claims, letters for collections etc. Such letters are always strictly formal and follow a structure and pattern of formalities.

- **Official Letter:** This type of letter is written to inform offices, branches, subordinates of official information. It usually relays official information like rules, regulations, procedures, events, or any other such information. Official letters are also formal in nature and follow certain structure and decorum.
- **Social Letter:** A personal letter written on the occasion of a special event is known as a social letter. Congratulatory letter, condolence letter, invitation letter etc. are all social letters.
- **Circular Letter:** A letter that announces information to a large number of people is a circular letter. The same letter is circulated to a large group of people to correspond some important information like a change of address, change in management, the retirement of a partner etc.
- **Employment Letters:** Any letters with respect to the employment process, like joining letter, promotion letter, application letter etc.

A complain letter is a written communication used to raise your concerns with a product, service or to address other types of grievances. The purpose of the letter is to address the problem and seek a productive resolution.

A clearly written, informative complaint letter accomplishes the following:

- it ensures the recipient knows about the situation
- it puts your complaint on record
- it lays the foundation in the event any legal steps must be taken

Describe the item or service you bought and the problem. Include serial or model numbers, and the name and location of the seller.

If you are following up on a conversation, be sure to say who you spoke with and confirm the details of your discussion.

THE FORMAT OF COMPLAIN LETTER

The format of your complain letter can help the right person correctly receive it.

A complains letter should start by including the following components:

- The date of the letter
- Your name, address and contact information
- The recipient's name, company name (if applicable)
- A professional salutation, using the recipient's name or their title(such as "Dear manager")
- A clear subject line (if sent as an email)

After writing these components, your first paragraph should define the problem, including descriptive information such as location and the date of occurrence.

The following paragraph should briefly explain how the problem can be rectified. If you have attached or included any receipts, photos or documents with your letter, you should mention them here.

DIFFERENT TYPES OF COMPLAIN LETTERS

You may need to send a complaint letter for a variety of situations. However, most of these letters fall into two primary categories:

Personal complaint letters: These letters of complaint are written by an individual consumer and usually concern a grievance with a product or a service. These individuals may be seeking a refund or a replacement for themselves, or they may be writing about an issue that affects other people as well.

Professional complaint letters: These letters are written by or on behalf of a company

or an organization and usually concern a problem with professional products or services or binding contracts made by them. When might a letter of complaint be sent? It might be when someone has done something wrong. Sometimes people write letters to organisations or the newspapers to complain about litter or poor service.

Letter writing is an essential skill. Despite the prevalence of emails and text messages, everyone has to write letters at some point. Letters of complaint, job applications, thank you letters, letters requesting changes or making suggestions — the list goes on and on. Encouraging children to write letters from an early age will improve their communication, social and handwriting skills, and teach them what they need to know about writing and structuring letters.

A well-written letter, without a doubt, has the best chance of succeeding. To ensure that your letter truly shines, it must be error-free and create the appropriate tone. Use any writing assistance to detect spelling and grammatical errors, and provide formatting tips and guidance to help you produce clear, easy-to-follow emails that keep your recipient's attention. Write the perfect letter and stand out for your amazing choice of words and structure.

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